

Supply chain management in the construction industry: a systematic literature review

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Abstract

The construction industry is one of the oldest industries; still many researches show its low productivity. Supply Chain Management (SCM) has been identified as a key area for increasing productivity in this industry. Therefore, in this paper we present a systematic literature review about the development of the SCM concept within the construction industry. Our analyses show a growing interest for the topic. Moreover, in line with the multidisciplinary character of SCM as a discipline, we found the main journals to be open to contributions using different perspectives. The citation network also shows a compact network, witnessing that authors from different fields cite each other. However, our analysis has also shown how sustainability and ICT are the most recent and faster growing topics, but still not very well integrated with the other concepts. Furthermore, the main path analysis highlighted non-linear development of the core literature. As a consequence, the construction industry appears to be for SCM an application or a context of study, and lacks of the character of a discipline, differently, for instance, from the automotive industry.

Keywords: supply chain management, construction industry, systematic literature review.

Introduction and background

The construction industry is one of the oldest industries; still many researches show its low productivity (Fulford and Standing, 2014). Supply chain management (SCM) has been identified as a key area for increasing productivity in this industry (Vrijhoef and Koskela, 2000). However, the peculiar characteristics of the construction industry make the application of traditional SCM practices a daunting task. Among these characteristics, we can highlight: temporariness and fragmentation of the supply

network, variability due to the large number of stakeholders and correlation to economic cycles, traditional low orientation towards collaboration, change inertia (Behera et al., 2015). To overcome these issues, the literature highlighted the importance of partnering relationships and collaboration (Bygballe et al., 2010).

Interestingly, the construction SCM topic has been analysed from different points of view, namely, strategy, logistics, construction project management (PM), ICT, purchasing management. More in detail, the literature on strategy highlights the advantages, barriers and enablers for partnership with suppliers (Venselaar et al., 2015). Next, the logistics perspective focuses on material flow management and warehousing (Childerkouse et al., 2003). The PM community, instead, highlights the importance of pre-project phases (e.g., tendering) and project procurement in relation to the execution of the project (Khalfan et al., 2011). After that, researchers in construction ICT analysed the application of extended ERP, building information modelling (BIM) and e-Procurement technologies in fostering efficiency and collaboration in the SC (Bowden et al., 2006; Brewer and Gajendran, 2009; Brewer et al., 2013). Finally, researchers in purchasing management have highlighted the importance of managing suppliers in the construction industry with mature purchasing management approaches (Van Lith et al., 2015).

Starting from this background, by means of a systematic literature review (SLR) in this paper we explore the different perspectives used to analyse SCM in the construction sector and their evolution over time. Moreover, we highlight the most recent trends and findings for each perspective, hence drawing the most promising future developments for the field.

Design

To understand trends and detect gaps in the scientific literature, we opted for a SLR. In contrast to the traditional or narrative literature review, a SLR uses a more rigorous and well-defined approach to review the literature in a specific domain. Following the guidelines provided by the literature (Kitchenham and Brereton, 2013)(Khan et al., 2003), we selected 641 articles published in Scopus-indexed journals on December 24th 2015 using the following criteria:

- “Supply chain” and “construction” in title, abstract or keywords;
- No time restriction;
- Only articles in English;
- Only in the following domains: Business, Management and Accounting, Computer Science, Decision Sciences, Economics, Econometrics and Finance, Engineering, Environmental Science, Multidisciplinary, Social Science

Then, we short-listed 252 articles looking at the title and abstract (and the entire paper when needed). The top 10 journals in terms of number of articles retrieved are listed in Table 1. The total number of papers per year is reported in Figure 1, where a clear positive trend is visible.

Table 1 – Journals with more than 10 papers in the corpus

Journal	1996-2000	2001-2005	2006-2010	2011-2015	Total
Construction Management and Economics	4	10	4	8	26
Automation in Construction	-	3	6	11	20
Supply Chain Management	2	3	9	3	17
Journal of Construction Engineering and Management	-	1	3	10	14
Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	-	-	6	8	14
International Journal of Project Management	-	2	5	5	12
European Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management	5	5	-	-	10

Figure 1 – Number of papers per year

We focused our analysis on the keywords. SCOPUS provides two typologies of keywords for each paper: authors' and index keywords. Authors' keywords are those directly provided by the authors in the paper, while index keywords are generated by the journals based on a standard thesaurus. Authors' keywords can be considered more accurate because the authors know the key contents of the paper, however they can be biased on what the authors think is more important. For instance, "purchasing management" can be considered not relevant by the authors if the article is published on the "Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management"; however, this keyword is important for our aims. Therefore, we considered both authors and index keywords jointly; in the reminder, we will refer generally to them as *keywords*. For future developments of this work, we will test the robustness of our results when using only authors' or index keywords.

We first extracted all the unique keywords from the corpus, getting 1670 keywords. 870 keywords were excluded from the analysis because they were too generic or not relevant (e.g., "academic community", "adoption", "preference order"). The remaining 800 keywords were aggregated into the following six categories we defined upon the literature review:

- STRATEGY: SC strategy, relationship, configuration, collaboration, partnership, trust, information sharing, integration, networks, modularization, fragmentation, lean, agile, governance;
- LOGISTICS: logistics, material management, inventory, reverse logistics, transportation, closed-loop, operations, consolidation, just-in-time;
- PM: Project management, quality, time, stakeholder, change management, concurrent engineering;
- PURCHASING MANAGEMENT: Purchasing, procurement, supplier management, tendering, outsourcing;
- ICT: eBusiness, eProcurement, communication, technology, BIM, RFID, GPS, virtual.

During our analysis, we identified other keywords potentially relevant that were classified after several iterations in the following categories:

- PERFORMANCE: Benchmarking, performance measurement, cost, time, quality issues;
- FINANCE: Financial aspects and performance;
- DESIGN: Product design, modularization;
- SUSTAINABILITY: Life cycle, waste, sustainable construction;
- METHOD: Methodology (case studies, survey, modelling);
- GEO: Focus on a geographical area;
- PUBLIC: Public projects/issues;
- SMEs: Small and medium enterprises;
- THEORY: theoretical approach employed (e.g., dynamic capabilities, ecosystems, industrial dynamics).

It is important to remind that each keyword was classified into only one of the previous categories. The count of the keywords for each category is reported in Table 2.

Table 2 – Categories of keywords

Category	Keywords count
STRATEGY	92
LOGISTICS	58
PM	52
PERFORMANCE	77
PROCUREMENT	52
ICT	157
FINANCE	9
DESIGN	29
SUSTAINABILITY	84
METHOD	107
GEO	51
PUBLIC	10
SMEs	8
THEORY	14

We excluded from the analysis “Finance”, “Design”, “Public”, “SMEs” and “Theory” because of their low count compared to the other categories. In this stage of the research we also excluded “Design”, “Geo” and “Performance”, because they are transversal topics and not specific to a research domain. However, we kept “Sustainability” in the analysis given its relevance in terms of number of keywords and its relatedness with SCM (Dadhich et al., 2015).

Following the keywords aggregation, we used the same keywords categories to classify each paper according to its keywords. As a result, a paper can belong to different keywords categories: for instance, a paper can have three keywords falling into the STRATEGY categories, five falling into the ICT category and two into the SUSTAINABILITY category. At this stage, we dropped 18 papers, as they did not have any relevant keyword with respect to the considered categories.

Findings

Step 1: journal and categories

We found a quite even distribution of the keywords categories across the journals. Not surprisingly, *Automation in Construction*, has the highest share of the ICT category, while the *European Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, the highest share of PURCHASING and SUSTAINABILITY. Interestingly, however, all the other journals have a quite mixed presence of the different topics, witnessing a convergence of the main journals.

Figure 2 – Distribution of the keyword categories across the most recurrent journals

Step 2: keywords analysis

In a second step of the study, we analysed the evolution over time of the keyword categories (Figure 3). We can observe that after 2006, ICT increased substantially its relevance, whereas SUSTAINABILITY and PURCHASING have been addressed more frequently after 2009 and 2012, respectively. Among the other categories, LOGISTICS has the lowest share, while STRATEGY and PM have quite stable and similar shares.

Figure 3 – Evolution of the categories over time

Step 3: Co-evolution of the categories

As a third step, we performed a multidimensional scaling to understand the closeness and co-evolution of the different categories. The multidimensional scaling is a two-step procedure which aims to represent in a bi-dimensional space the distance between different concepts, in our case the different categories. As a first step, this procedure calculates the average distance between each couple of categories in a space where the number of dimensions is equal to the number of papers and the coordinates are given by the number occurrences of a category in each paper. For instance, two categories which appear in the same papers will be very close because they will have similar coordinates. On the other side, categories which appear in different papers will be further away. In our case, the distance between the categories was calculated as the Euclidean distance. In this way, a $n \times n$ matrix is created, where n is the number of the categories and the cells are filled with the distances between couplets of categories. After that, the multidimensional scaling projects the n -dimensional space in two dimensions, trying to keep the distance between couplets of categories as close as possible to the original matrix. We used this analysis to see the evolution in the categories, so we split the sample into two subgroups: 1998-2006 and 2007-2015 and performed two separate analyses (Figure 4). As we can see, in the first period (1998-2006) the topics were quite disconnected among each other. In other words, papers tended to focus on one topic at a time. SUSTAINABILITY was close to LOGISTICS, but this is not very significant given the very few papers dealing with sustainability. On the contrary, in the period 2007-2015, we can see how STRATEGY, PROCUREMENT, PM, LOGISTICS get very closed, witnessing an increase of the papers dealing with two or more of these topics at the same time. However, ICT and SUSTAINABILITY remain quite isolated, witnessing opportunities for better integration in the future.

Figure 4 – Multidimensional scaling of the keywords categories in the two periods considered

Step 4: Citation Network (CN)

The CN (Figure 5) allows to better understand the relationships between the papers in the corpus. We can see a lack of isolated clusters, thus witnessing that scholars from the different disciplines are aware of the work in the other fields.

Figure 5 – The citation network

Finally, we extracted the main path resulted from the CN analysis (Wilding et al., 2012) (Lucio-Arias and Leydesdorff, 2008) (Figure 6). The main path enabled to identify the main contributions in the development of the scientific field over time. The

first papers introduce the concept of SC in the construction industry while the last ones the concept of modularization and category management (Table 3). However, the main path also shows that the development of the discipline did not follow a clear direction. Rather, each paper provides a different perspective. Some papers (Doran and Giannakis, 2011), for instance, use the construction industry as a setting in which to test models or to provide empirical evidence which can be useful in different contexts.

Figure 6 – The main path identified in the citation network.

Table 3 – Papers in the main path

Authors	Title	Year	Source title
Kornelius L., Wamelink J.W.F.	The virtual corporation: Learning from construction	1998	Supply Chain Management
Agapiou A., Flanagan R., Norman G., Notman D.	The changing role of builders merchants in the construction supply chain	1998	Construction Management and Economics
Saad M., Jones M., James P.	A review of the progress towards the adoption of supply chain management (SCM) relationships in construction	2002	European Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management
Xue X., Li X., Shen Q., Wang Y.	An agent-based framework for supply chain coordination in construction	2005	Automation in Construction
Xue X., Wang Y., Shen Q., Yu X.	Coordination mechanisms for construction supply chain management in the Internet environment	2007	International Journal of Project Management
Bankvall L., Bygballe L.E., Dubois A., Jahre M.	Interdependence in supply chains and projects in construction	2010	Supply Chain Management
Doran D., Giannakis M.	An examination of a modular supply chain: A construction sector perspective	2011	Supply Chain Management
Tennant S., Fernie S.	Organizational learning in construction supply chains	2013	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management
Jonsson H., Rudberg M.	Classification of production systems for industrialized building: A production strategy perspective	2014	Construction Management and Economics

Conclusions

In this paper, we performed a systematic literature review to study the development of the SCM concept within the construction industry literature. Our results primarily show a growing interest for the topic. Moreover, in line with the multidisciplinary character of SCM as a discipline, we found the main journals to be open to contributions using different perspectives. The citation network also showed a compact network, witnessing that authors from different fields cite each other. However, our analysis has also shown how sustainability and ICT are the most recent and faster growing topics, but still not very well integrated with the other concepts. Furthermore, the main path analysis highlighted non-linear development of the core literature. As a consequence, the construction industry appears to be for SCM an application or a context of study, and lacks of the character of a discipline. The evidence provided by recent researches about the poor performance of construction supply chains highlights that this is a relevant issue and additional work is needed to provide *normative* contributions which integrate all the different disciplines.

This work is of course not free of limitations. First of all, we focused our analysis on the keywords. Next, our analyses are still descriptive and more in-depth analysis is required on the content of the papers.

Future developments of this work include the citation analysis at the journal level and a deeper analysis of the citation network, using the indicators of closeness and centrality. Moreover, an additional effort is required to clearly trace the most promising avenues for future research.

References

- Behera, P., Mohanty, R.P., Prakash, A., (2015), "Understanding Construction Supply Chain Management", *Production Planning and Control* Vol. 26, No. 16, pp. 1332-1350.
- Bowden, S., Dorr, A., Thorpe, T., Anumba, C., (2006), "Mobile ICT support for construction process improvement", *Automation in Construction* Vol. 15, No. 5, pp. 664-676.
- Brewer, G., Gajendran, T., (2009), "Emerging ICT trends in construction project teams: A Delphi survey", *Electronic Journal of Information Technology in Construction* Vol. 14, pp. 81-97.
- Brewer, G., Gajendran, T., Runeson, G., (2013), "ICT & innovation: A case of integration in a regional construction firm", *Australasian Journal of Construction Economics and Building* Vol. 13, No. 3, pp. 24-36.
- Bygballe, L.E., Jahre, M., Swärd, A., (2010), "Partnering relationships in construction: A literature review", *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management* Vol. 16, No. 4, pp. 239-253.
- Childerkouse, P., Lewis, J., Naim, M., Towill, D.R., (2003), "Re-engineering a construction supply chain: A material flow control approach", *Supply Chain Management* Vol. 8, No. 4, pp. 395-406.
- Dadhich, P., Genovese, A., Kumar, N., Acquaye, A., (2015), "Developing sustainable supply chains in the UK construction industry: A case study", *International Journal of Production Economics* Vol. 164, pp. 271-284.
- Doran, D., Giannakis, M., (2011), "An examination of a modular supply chain: A construction sector perspective", *Supply Chain Management* Vol. 16, No. 4, pp. 260-270.
- Fulford, R., Standing, C., (2014), "Construction industry productivity and the potential for collaborative practice", *International Journal of Project Management* Vol. 32, No. 2, pp. 315-326.
- Khalfan, M.M.A., Maqsood, T., Arif, M., (2011), "Relationships among supply chain participants in different methods of project procurement", *Malaysian Construction Research Journal* Vol. 9, No. 2, pp. 73-88.

- Khan, K.S., Kunz, R., Kleijnen, J., Antes, G., (2003), "Five steps to conducting a systematic review", *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine* Vol. 96, No. 3, pp. 118-121.
- Kitchenham, B., Brereton, P., (2013), "A systematic review of systematic review process research in software engineering", *Information and software technology* Vol. 55, No. 12, pp. 2049-2075.
- Lucio-Arias, D., Leydesdorff, L., (2008), "Main-path analysis and path-dependent transitions in HistCite™-based historiograms", *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology* Vol. 59, No. 12, pp. 1948-1962.
- Van Lith, J., Voordijk, H., Castano, J.M., Vos, B., (2015), "Assessing maturity development of purchasing management in construction", *Benchmarking* Vol. 22, No. 6, pp. 1033-1057.
- Venselaar, M., Gruis, V., Verhoeven, F., (2015), "Implementing supply chain partnering in the construction industry: Work floor experiences within a Dutch housing association", *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management* Vol. 21, No. 1, pp. 1-8.
- Vrijhoef, R., Koskela, L., (2000), "The four roles of supply chain management in construction", *European journal of purchasing & supply management* Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 169-178.
- Wilding, R., Wagner, B., Colicchia, C., Strozzi, F., (2012), "Supply chain risk management: a new methodology for a systematic literature review", *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal* Vol. 17, No. 4, pp. 403-418.